

1 **Title**

2 Improving biorisk management knowledge and application among laboratory professionals
3 from the 16 regions of Ghana: A Socratic approach

4 **Authors**

5 Richard Kutame^{1*}, Charles Quaye², Bernard Nkrumah³, Nathaniel Frimpong Boateng²,
6 Rexford Adade¹, Gifty Boateng¹

7 ¹National Public Health and Reference Laboratory, Ghana Health Service, Korle-Bu, Accra,
8 Ghana

9 ²Noguchi Memorial Institute for Medical Research, University of Ghana, Legon, Accra,
10 Ghana

11 ³Africa Field Epidemiology Network, Accra, Ghana

12

13 *Corresponding author: Richard Kutame, richard.kutame@ghs.gov.gh

14

15

16

17

18

19

20

21

22

23

24

25

26

27

28

29

30

31

32

33

34

35

36

37

38

39

40

41

42

43

44

45

46

47

48

49

50 **Abstract**

51 **Background**

52 Effective biorisk management (BRM) in medical laboratories is essential for safety and
53 public health, yet knowledge and implementation gaps persist, particularly in resource-
54 limited settings including Ghana. This study assessed the impact of a BRM training program
55 on participants' knowledge, attitudes, and readiness to implement BRM practices in Ghana.

56 **Intervention**

57 A structured BRM training using the Socratic approach was conducted for medical laboratory
58 professionals across 16 regions. The program covered BRM principles, risk assessment,
59 mitigation strategies, and regulatory compliance. Knowledge gains were assessed through
60 formative evaluations, while participant feedback highlighted implementation challenges and
61 support needs.

62 **Lessons Learnt**

63 Training significantly improved participants' BRM knowledge and confidence. Many
64 expressed readiness to implement risk assessments, control measures, and documentation
65 improvements. However, logistical and financial constraints, along with regional and rank-
66 based disparities, may hinder sustained implementation. Continuous capacity-building efforts
67 are needed to address these challenges.

68 **Recommendations**

69 To enhance impact, policymakers should prioritize sustained BRM education, resource
70 allocation, and targeted follow-up interventions. Regular refresher courses and mentorship
71 programs can reinforce learning and bridge gaps. Institutional commitment and integration of
72 BRM into routine laboratory operations are essential for long-term sustainability.

73 **What this study adds**

74 This study demonstrates the effectiveness of BRM training in Ghana, emphasizing
75 knowledge gains and implementation challenges. It informs laboratory systems
76 strengthening, policy development, and capacity-building efforts. Addressing regional and
77 rank-based disparities can improve training outcomes, enhancing laboratory safety, risk
78 management, and compliance with international standards.

79

80 **Keywords:**

81 Biorisk Management, Laboratory Safety, Socratic Approach, Capacity Building, Risk
82 Assessment, Laboratory Strengthening

83

84

85

86

87

88

89

90

91

92

93

94

95

96

97

98

99

100 **1.0 Background**

101 Biorisk management (BRM) encompasses the systematic application of management policies,
102 procedures, and practices to analyze, evaluate, and control risks associated with biological
103 agents and toxins. The World Health Organization (WHO) and other organizations have
104 emphasized the importance of a comprehensive biorisk management system, integrating both
105 biosafety and biosecurity to ensure that laboratory operations do not pose risks to health, safety,
106 or the environment [1].

107 Recent happenings such as Ebola virus outbreak, COVID-19 pandemic and others have
108 highlighted the need for tailored biorisk management systems in resource-limited settings.
109 Factors such as the availability of resources, cultural considerations, and existing infrastructure
110 play crucial roles in the effectiveness of an established biorisk management system. There is
111 also an emphasis on continuous education and training for laboratory staff to enhance their
112 understanding of biorisk management and to ensure compliance with international standards
113 [2].

114 The regulatory landscape for biorisk management has evolved significantly over the past few
115 years. International organizations such as WHO, US Centers for Disease Control and
116 Prevention (CDC), and the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) have
117 developed guidelines to reflect new challenges and advancements in the field [1]. These
118 guidelines have been broadly used in laboratories and biomedical sectors at all levels as
119 standards that represent best practices in biosafety [3-5]. Furthermore, they have been usually
120 recommended and adapted to the local context in several instances [6-7].

121 Current data about laboratory incidents is difficult to obtain as there is not yet a standardized
122 system for reporting of laboratory incidents in many countries including Ghana [8]. Laboratory
123 incident reporting faces challenges such as underreporting due to fear of blame and lack of
124 standardized procedures. Limited awareness about reporting systems and unclear guidelines
125 have also been described to often hinder accurate reporting. Additionally, inadequate training
126 on incident documentation and lack of follow-up reduces opportunities for improvement and
127 risk mitigation [9].

128 The Ghana Health Service recently developed a biorisk management guideline to support
129 laboratories in the development and implementation of biosafety and biosecurity activities [10].
130 A survey conducted in a public health reference laboratory in Ghana recommended training
131 and sustained oversight supervision of laboratory staff as a means of strengthening indicators
132 for biorisk management [11].

133 Various training approaches such as the Socratic approach and the active learning approach
134 have been used to create awareness, enhance knowledge and ensure laboratory safety on biorisk
135 management. These approaches involve the use of structured lectures, demonstrations, hands-
136 on sessions, and evaluations through multiple-choice questions, theoretical examinations, and
137 feedback collected via a Likert scale [12-14].

138 We used the Socratic approach to develop and execute a national training program in biorisk
139 management for laboratory professionals in all 16 regions of Ghana. We assessed the impact
140 of structured BRM training program on participants' knowledge, attitudes, and readiness to
141 implement BRM practices in Ghana. In this paper, we report the lessons learnt and
142 recommendations from this training program.

143 **2.0 Description of intervention**

144 **2.1 Ethical consideration**

145 The training program described in this article did not require ethical clearance as it focused
146 solely on professional capacity building without involving human subjects' research. However,

147 ethical clearance was applied for through the Institutional Review Board of the Christian Health
148 Association of Ghana (CHAG) (pending approval) to allow for the use of the data collected as
149 part of this training.

150 **2.2 Setting**

151 Ghana operates a tiered laboratory system from subdistrict to national level. There are 16
152 administrative regions and 261 districts. Laboratory services are provided across the various
153 tiers. It is estimated that there are about 1500 laboratories, comprising both public and private.

154 **2.3 Training approach**

155 We developed a standardized five-day training program with eight contact hours per day. A
156 team of laboratory experts and five trainers were selected to develop the training program based
157 on the following criteria: biorisk management certification by the International Federation of
158 Biosafety Associations (IFBA), expertise in biorisk management, extensive laboratory
159 experience and strong facilitation skills.

160 The training program was implemented in two phases: phase one was an initial training-of-
161 trainers (ToT) and phase two was a regional rollout across all 16 regions in Ghana. The Socratic
162 approach was used to develop training content, materials, and deliver training of selected
163 medical laboratory professionals. Participants were engaged in practical scenarios, analysis of
164 potential risks, and collaborative development of management strategies, focusing on key
165 aspects of biorisk management, such as risk assessment, mitigation strategies, and emergency
166 response.

167 The Socratic approach was chosen for its emphasis on interactive discussions, critical thinking,
168 and real-world application of concepts. Unlike passive learning approaches, it encourages
169 professionals to question assumptions, assess risks, and solve problems which are key to
170 effective biosafety decisions. While other methods, like active learning, yield strong results,
171 the Socratic approach's inquiry-driven nature best supports practical decision-making in
172 biorisk management.

173 **2.4 Study population and sampling strategy**

174 For phase one, two senior-level participants were selected from each of the 16 regions. Official
175 invitations were sent to regional administration to nominate qualified personnel based on
176 specified criteria. Participants were selected based on their involvement in BRM activities, and
177 prior facilitation experience. All participants enrolled in the ToT were required to pass a
178 qualification exam with a minimum score of 70% to assist with the regional roll-out.

179 For phase two, two participants were selected from each of the 261 districts through official
180 invitation based on their job roles, field experience, and commitment to professional
181 development. The regional administration was involved in the selection to create ownership
182 and accountability.

183 **2.5. Training programme**

184 ***2.5.1 Development of training content***

185 Internationally recognized training modules such as the IFBA guidelines, the WHO biosafety
186 manual and other associated monographs were integrated with local needs to create eight
187 comprehensive modules. Practical scenarios and relevant case studies formed the basis of the
188 curriculum. Open-ended questions were used to develop the modules to stimulate discussion
189 and deepen participants' understanding of biorisk management principles. Supplementary
190 materials, including regulatory guidelines and multimedia resources were curated to enhance
191 the learning experience.

192 **2.5.2 Module description**

193 The training program consisted of eight modules. Each module focused on a specific aspect of
194 biorisk management. The modules are:

- 195 1) Introduction to Biorisk Management: Understanding biosafety, biosecurity, and risk
196 classification in laboratory settings.
- 197 2) Biosafety Guidelines and Regulations: Overview of national and international biosafety
198 regulations and compliance requirements.
- 199 3) Risk Assessment in Biorisk Management: Identifying hazards, evaluating risks, and
200 implementing control measures in laboratory processes.
- 201 4) Laboratory Design and Engineering Controls: Infrastructure, containment strategies,
202 ventilation, and facility layout for biosafety.
- 203 5) Personal Protective Equipment (PPE): Types of PPE, proper selection, donning and
204 doffing techniques, and contamination prevention.
- 205 6) Safe Work Practices: Best practices for handling biohazards, decontamination, spill
206 response, and waste disposal.
- 207 7) Emergency Preparedness and Response Planning: Developing emergency response
208 plans, defining roles, and establishing incident management protocols.
- 209 8) Incident Response and Case Studies: Analyzing real-life biosafety incidents, discussing
210 containment strategies, and reviewing lessons learned.

211 **2.5.3 Assessment of participants**

212 We conducted a self-assessment of participants using a modified version of the Global
213 Laboratory Leadership Programme's (GLLP) proficiency level tool [15]. This structured tool
214 ensured a thorough evaluation of participants' proficiency across key biorisk management
215 domains. Formative assessments were conducted through pre- and post-training tests as well
216 as discussions. Additionally, summative assessments through development and presentation of
217 individual action plans were conducted. Post-training score of 70% and above was considered
218 as the passing score. We evaluated the effectiveness of the Socratic approach in biorisk
219 management education by conducting surveys that captured participants' perceptions, content
220 relevance, and overall satisfaction.

221 **2.6. Data management and analysis**

222 We electronically administered self-assessments, pre- and post-training tests, and qualification
223 exams using Microsoft Forms 365 (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, WA 98052-6399, USA).
224 Data collected were exported into Microsoft Excel 365 (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, WA
225 98052-6399, USA), cleaned, and analyzed using Jupyter Notebook 6.5.2 (Jupyter Team) with
226 Python 3 (Python Software Foundation), and R Studio 1.1.414 (RStudio, 250 Northern Ave
227 Suite 420 Boston, MA 02210) with R version 3.4.3 [16], and Microsoft Excel 365.

228 Anonymized data were analyzed quantitatively, including descriptive analysis of the
229 participant information, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for comparing mean scores across
230 groups, and paired-samples t-tests for evaluating individual pre- and post-test score differences.
231 Statistical significance was evaluated using p-value of $p < 0.05$. Data was presented in both
232 tabular and graphical forms, as appropriate.

233 **3. Lessons learnt**

234 **3.1. Training-of-trainers (ToT)**

235 A total of 32 participants were selected for the ToT training. There were more males (28/32)
236 than females (4/32). The post-test score was significantly higher (54%; $p < 0.05$) than the pre-
237 test score. Majority of the participants, 72% (23/32), scored above the pass mark of 70% (Table
238 1).

239 Table 1: Results of analysis of pre- and post-test scores during training-of-trainers phase

Parameter	Pre-Test Score	Post-Test Score
Average score	12	19
Minimum score	9	15
Maximum score	16	20
Median score	12.5	20
No. of participants with score \geq average (%)	22 (69%)	23 (72%)
Average Increase (%)	54%	
Paired t-test (p-value)	1.25 x 10 ⁻¹⁷	
Score %	Frequency (%)	
80-90	7 (21.9)	
70-79	16 (50.0)	
60-69	7 (21.9)	
<60	1(3.1)	

240

241 **3.2. Regional Roll Out**

242 A total of 532 participants were trained across the country. Ashanti region had the highest
 243 number of participants (86/532) whilst Ahafo and North East regions had the least participants
 244 (12/532) respectively (Figure 1).

245

246

247 Figure 1: Regional distribution of participants in the roll-out training

248

249 **3.2.1. Self Evaluation**

250 About 82.3% (438/532) of participants responded to the pre-workshop self-evaluation
 251 questionnaire. Medical Laboratory Scientists constituted the largest cadre, 34.9% (153/532)
 252 (Table 2).

253 Table 2: Cadre distribution of participants in the regional roll-out training

Grade	Frequency	Percent
Chief Medical Laboratory Scientist	1	0.2
Deputy Chief Medical Laboratory Scientist	27	6.2
Principal Medical Laboratory Scientist	50	11.4
Senior Medical Laboratory Scientist	76	17.4
Medical Laboratory Scientist	153	34.9
Other	131	29.9
Total	438	100

254
 255 Most participants were at the beginner level across most indicators, with indicator 2 having the
 256 highest proportion of beginners, 65.3% (286/438), and indicator 13 having the least, 36.3%
 257 (159/438). Expert level participants were highest for indicator 9, 7.5% (33/438) but least for
 258 indicators 5 and 19, 0.9% (4/438) respectively. Majority of the participants were not
 259 knowledgeable in risk assessment and hazard identification. The skilled level was most
 260 frequent for indicator 13, 53.7% (235/438) (Table 3).

261 Table 3: Participants' self-evaluation of awareness and knowledge of key biorisk management
 262 domains prior to the regional roll-out training

No.	Indicators	Not Knowledgeable (%)	Beginner (%)	Skilled (%)	Expert (%)
Biosafety basics					
1	I understand the concept of biosafety and its importance in laboratory settings.	22 (5%)	283 (64.6%)	123 (28.1%)	10 (2.3%)
2	I am aware of the different Biosafety Levels (BSLs) and their corresponding containment requirements.	42 (9.6%)	286 (65.3%)	102 (23.3%)	8 (1.8%)
3	I can differentiate between biological agents classified under different risk groups.	55 (12.6%)	265 (60.5%)	113 (25.8%)	5 (1.1%)
Risk assessment and hazard identification					
4	I know how to conduct a risk assessment to identify potential hazards in a laboratory.	93 (21.2%)	264 (60.3%)	75 (17.1%)	6 (1.4%)
5	I understand the process of assigning Biosafety Levels based on risk assessment.	100 (22.8%)	265 (60.5%)	69 (15.8%)	4 (0.9%)
6	I am familiar with the factors to consider when determining appropriate containment measures.	105 (24%)	261 (59.6%)	66 (15.1%)	6 (1.4%)
Personal Protective Equipment					
7	I can list the types of PPE required for different laboratory tasks.	21 (4.8%)	187 (42.7%)	210 (47.9%)	20 (4.6%)
8	I know how to correctly don, doff, and dispose of PPE.	39 (8.9%)	210 (47.9%)	174 (39.7%)	15 (3.4%)
9	I understand the importance of proper PPE usage in minimizing exposure risks.	16 (3.7%)	171 (39%)	218 (49.8%)	33 (7.5%)
Laboratory design and engineering controls					
10	I am aware of the design principles for biosafety laboratories, including ventilation and containment measures.	71 (16.2%)	261 (59.6%)	98 (22.4%)	8 (1.8%)

11	I understand the function and proper usage of biological safety cabinets, fume hoods, and other containment equipment.	55 (12.6%)	265 (60.5%)	110 (25.1%)	8 (1.8%)
Safe work practices and procedures					
12	I know the procedures for safely handling and disposing of biological materials and hazardous chemicals.	36 (8.2%)	244 (55.7%)	148 (33.8%)	10 (2.3%)
13	I understand the importance of hand hygiene, proper lab techniques, and minimizing aerosol generation.	14 (3.2%)	159 (36.3%)	235 (53.7%)	30 (6.8%)
14	I am familiar with decontamination procedures for surfaces, equipment, and materials.	17 (3.9%)	170 (38.8%)	221 (50.5%)	30 (6.8%)
Emergency preparedness and response					
15	I know the steps to take during laboratory emergencies, including fires, spills, and biological exposures.	33 (7.5%)	249 (56.8%)	144 (32.9%)	12 (2.7%)
16	I am aware of the location of emergency exits, fire extinguishers, eyewash stations, and emergency showers in my laboratory.	26 (5.9%)	179 (40.9%)	199 (45.4%)	34 (7.8%)
Incident reporting and documentation					
17	I understand the significance of reporting incidents and near-misses related to biorisk management.	38 (8.7%)	229 (52.3%)	161 (36.8%)	10 (2.3%)
18	I know how to complete incident reports accurately and provide essential details.	81 (18.5%)	252 (57.5%)	100 (22.8%)	5 (1.1%)
Regulation and guidelines					
19	I am familiar with relevant biosafety regulations and guidelines in my region or field.	106 (24.2%)	244 (55.7%)	84 (19.2%)	4 (0.9%)
20	I understand the importance of complying with regulatory requirements for laboratory safety.	38 (8.7%)	222 (50.7%)	164 (37.4%)	14 (3.2%)

263

264 3.2.2 Pre- and Post-Training Assessments

265 There was a statistically significant increase in mean scores from 57.9% to 73.7% ($p < 0.001$)
 266 (Table 4). In the pre-test, Volta region had the highest median score (70.0%) whilst Savannah
 267 and Western North regions had the least (50.0%). In the post-test, however, the highest median
 268 score was recorded in Oti and Western North regions respectively (85.0%) and the least was
 269 recorded in Upper East (65.0%) (Figure 2 and 3).

270 Table 4: Paired t-test results comparing pre- and post-test assessment scores in percentage

Statistic	Pre-test	Post-test
Mean (Range)	57.9 (0 – 90.0)	73.7 (20.0 – 100.0)
Std. Dev.	13.8	11.8
T-test	-17.525	
P-value	2.93×10^{-53}	

271

272
 273 Figure 2: Boxplot of the distribution of pre-test scores in percentage by region
 274

275
 276 Figure 3: Boxplot of the distribution of post-test scores in percentage by region
 277

278 **3.2.3. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)**

279 There were significant differences in pre-test scores across 15 regions and participants' current
 280 rank respectively ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, there were significant differences, in post-test
 281 scores across the 14 regions and participants' current rank ($p < 0.05$) (Table 5).

282

283 Table 5: ANOVA results for differences in mean percentage pre-test and post-test scores by
 284 region and current rank of participants

Variable	Sum of Squares	df	F	PR(>F)
Pre-test Assessment				
Region	16837.41	14	8.111388	6.95×10^{-16}
Residual	81548.26	550		
Post-test Assessment				
Region	11583.06	13	7.577611	1.25×10^{-13}
Residual	53735.83	457		
Current Rank	1950.28	5	2.862238	0.01474
Residual	63368.62	465		

285

286 **3.2.4 Training Evaluation**

287 Analysis of the participants' evaluation of the training indicated positive feedback across most
 288 criteria (Figure 4). However, about 5.6% (24/429) of participants expressed disagreement that
 289 the course length was appropriate and 0.9% (4/427) disagreed that the course met their
 290 expectations (Figure 4).

291

292 Figure 4: Distribution of participants' responses to evaluation questionnaire: A) The objectives
293 of the training were met, B) The presenters were engaging, C) The presentation materials were
294 relevant, D) The content was organised and easy to follow, E) The trainers were well prepared
295 and able to answer any questions, F) The course length was appropriate, G) The training met
296 your expectations
297

298 **4. Recommendations**

299 This paper reports lessons learnt and recommendations from the use of the Socratic approach
300 to develop and execute a national training program in biorisk management for laboratory
301 professionals in all 16 regions of Ghana. The impact of the structured BRM training program
302 on participants' knowledge, attitudes, and readiness to implement BRM practices in Ghana was
303 presented.

304 There were significant differences in both pre-test and post-test performance by region,
305 suggesting that participants' baseline knowledge and the effectiveness of the training varied
306 geographically. The persistence of these differences from pre-test to post-test may reflect the
307 training's differential effectiveness across regions. It may also be a reflection of the differing
308 levels of access to prior training, resources, facilitator selection or support systems in
309 different regions.

310 Rank-based analysis showed significant variation in the measured performance, suggesting that
311 participants' professional cadre influenced their knowledge both before and after the training.
312 Higher-ranked participants may have had more prior exposure to biorisk management,
313 contributing to higher initial scores and potentially more pronounced learning gains. This
314 finding may imply that continuous professional development programmes through on-the-job
315 training in BRM could consolidate the gains from this training.

316 Additionally, results from the t-test showed that not only did the average scores improve but
317 also there was a reduction in the variability of scores among participants. The findings
318 suggested the training might have led to a significant improvement in awareness of BRM
319 among participants and improvement was relatively consistent across participants. This was
320 also reflected in the results of the analysis of variance to the effect that variations across region
321 and current rank were relatively less pronounced in the post-test.

322 Alternatively, the presence of significant outliers, especially in regional level distributions,
323 suggests that some participants may have had either exceptionally high or low scores that may
324 not be explained by the general trends. Further analysis of these outliers may identify any
325 underlying factors that might have influenced these extreme scores, such as specific local
326 challenges or individual participant circumstances.

327 Various approaches have been used to deliver training on biorisk management. For instance,
328 Muneer et al [12] utilized the Socratic approach in delivering their training programme and
329 reported on average increase in knowledge from 70%, among Pakistani students. Elhadidy et
330 al [13] used the active learning approach and reported a significant improvement among
331 faculty members handling biological materials in Egypt. Additionally, Qasmi et al. [14]
332 assessed the impact of a four-month biosecurity course on raising awareness among graduate
333 students and reported an 83.3% improvement in post-training assessments compared to pre-
334 training results. Despite the varied approaches used, these studies confirm the improvement
335 achieved when using a structured approach to deliver training in biorisk management. The
336 differences in the magnitude of outcomes may be explained by the differences in population
337 and sample sizes.

338 Analysis of the participants' feedback highlighted several key insights from the biorisk
339 management training. These insights could be grouped into thematic areas that reflect both
340 the successes and areas for improvement.

341 ***Successes***

342 Firstly, most comments expressed satisfaction with the training. Phrases like "very
343 impactful," "excellent training," "very useful," "great workshop," and "knowledge packed"
344 were recurring themes. A significant proportion (likely over 80%) of the feedback indicated
345 that the training was perceived as highly beneficial and impactful.

346
347 Secondly, facilitators were consistently praised for their knowledge, engagement, and
348 presentation skills. Phrases like "facilitators were on point," "very knowledgeable," and
349 "excellent deliveries" were common. It is safe to say that over 90% of comments that
350 mentioned the facilitators, provided positive feedback.

351
352 Thirdly, participants repeatedly highlighted the training's relevance to their work, particularly
353 in laboratory settings and healthcare. Many expressed that the training provided practical
354 knowledge and skills that they could immediately apply.

355 356 ***Areas for Improvement***

357 Some participants (estimated 20-25%) emphasized the need for post-training monitoring,
358 follow-up visits, and support for implementing learned practices. This indicates a critical gap
359 in ensuring the long-term effectiveness of the training.

360
361 Around 10-15% of comments suggested providing additional resources, such as tools,
362 materials, and training slides highlighting a need to enhance the practical aspects of the
363 training with more tangible resources.

364
365 An estimated 20% of participants requested that the training be expanded to include other
366 healthcare professionals, facility-level staff, and waste disposal agencies reflecting a
367 recognition of the importance of biorisk management across various sectors.

368
369 Around 10% of the comments requested for longer durations of the training, and more
370 practical sections to be added.

371 372 **4.1 Limitations**

373 Despite the insights reported in this paper, we acknowledge some limitations. Some
374 participants could not complete the electronic assessments due to the unavailability of internet
375 in certain locations and this may bias the findings. While the diverse backgrounds of
376 participants in terms of experience, location and responsibilities enriched discussions, this
377 diversity may also limit the generalizability of the findings to all laboratory settings. Finally,
378 resource constraints posed a challenge, as the Socratic approach's reliance on skilled
379 facilitators and extended time commitment might hinder the scalability of the training program.

380 **5. Conclusion**

381 The biorisk management training program significantly improved participants' knowledge and
382 understanding, with the Socratic approach and Training-of-Trainers (ToT) model proving
383 highly effective. The ToT program led to a statistically significant increase in post-test scores,
384 demonstrating successful knowledge acquisition and scalability. The nationwide rollout further

385 expanded reach, though regional and rank-based disparities indicate the need for targeted
386 follow-ups to strengthen laboratory safety and risk management practices.

387 To sustain impact, policies should prioritize ongoing capacity building, while practical efforts
388 should focus on tailored interventions that address specific regional and professional needs.
389 Ensuring structured risk management and continuous professional development will contribute
390 to safer laboratories. The program's success validates the training model while underscoring
391 the need to analyze participation patterns to inform resource allocation and maximize long-
392 term effectiveness.

393 **Acknowledgement**

394 We acknowledge all participants who took part in the surveys and provided feedback. We also
395 acknowledge the country team from the Clinton Health Access Initiative (CHAI) for supporting
396 the standardization of the presentation slides and organization of the ToT. We further
397 acknowledge all facilitators and regional teams that supported the regional roll-out.

398 **Competing interest**

399 The authors declare that they have no financial or personal relationship(s) that may have
400 inappropriately influenced them in writing this article.

401 **Author contributions**

402 R.K., G.B., C.Q., E.A., D.D.A. and F.S. designed the intervention; all authors contributed to
403 the implementation of the intervention. R.K. analysed the results and drafted the manuscript
404 with support from C.Q., B.N., and G.B. All authors provided critical feedback and contributed
405 to the final manuscript.

406 **Sources of support**

407 This activity was funded by the Global Fund under the COVID-19 Response Mechanism
408 Portfolio Optimization Wave 1 Grant.

409 **Data availability**

410 The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding
411 author, R.K. The data are not publicly available due to the need to control use of the data for
412 legitimate purposes.

413 **Disclaimer**

414 The views and opinions expressed in this article are those of the authors and are the product of
415 professional research. They do not necessarily reflect the official policy or position of any
416 affiliated institution, funder, agency, or that of the publisher. The authors are responsible for
417 this article's results, findings, and content.

418

419

420

421

422

423

424

425

426 **References**

- 427 1. World Health Organization. Laboratory biosafety manual. 4th ed. Geneva: WHO; 2020.
428 Available from: <https://www.who.int>.
- 429 2. Albtoush N, Noguez JH. Risk-based reboot: new WHO guidance for laboratory
430 biosafety. *Clin Chem*. 2018;64(10):1544-1545.
- 431 3. Bowolaksono A, Lestari F, Satyawardhani SA, Kadir A, Maharani CF, Paramitasari D.
432 Analysis of bio-risk management system implementation in Indonesian higher
433 education laboratory. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021;18(10):5076.
434 doi:10.3390/ijerph18105076.
- 435 4. International Organization for Standardization. ISO 35001:2019 Biorisk management
436 for laboratories and other related organizations. 1st ed. Switzerland: ISO; 2019.
437 Available from: <https://www.iso.org/standard/71293.html>.
- 438 5. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Biosafety in microbiological and
439 biomedical laboratories (BMBL). 6th ed. Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Health
440 and Human Services; 2020.
- 441 6. Callihan DR, et al. Considerations for laboratory biosafety and biosecurity during the
442 coronavirus disease 2019 pandemic: applying the ISO 35001:2019 standard and high-
443 reliability organizations principles. *Appl Biosaf*. 2021;26(3):113-122.
- 444 7. Dickmann P, et al. Biosafety and biosecurity: a relative risk-based framework for safer,
445 more secure, and sustainable laboratory capacity building. *Front Public Health*.
446 2015;3:241.
- 447 8. Keckler MS, et al. Development and implementation of evidence-based laboratory
448 safety management tools for a public health laboratory. *Saf Sci*. 2019;117:205-216.
- 449 9. Klemp K, Zwart D, Hansen J, Hellebek T, Luettel D, Verstappen W, Beyer M, Gerlach
450 FM, Hoffmann B, Esmail A. A safety incident reporting system for primary care: a
451 systematic literature review and consensus procedure by the LINNEAUS collaboration
452 on patient safety in primary care. *Eur J Gen Pract*. 2015;21 Suppl(sup1):39-44.
453 doi:10.3109/13814788.2015.1043728. PMID: 26339835; PMCID: PMC4828618.
- 454 10. Ghana Health Service (GHS). National biosafety and biosecurity guide for laboratories
455 in Ghana. 2023.
- 456 11. Agboyie DDA, Amedzro I, Ameme D, Bando D, Opare D, Boateng G, Sackey S,
457 Quarm JA, Kenu E, Afari E. Assessment of the biorisk management of a public health
458 reference laboratory, Northern Region, Ghana – 2018. Poster presented at: 10th
459 TEPHINET Global Conference; 2019 Oct 29; Stone Mountain Ballroom, USA.
460 Abstract ID: 346.
- 461 12. Muneer S, Kayani HA, Ali K, Asif E, Zohra RR, Kabir F. Laboratory biosafety and
462 biosecurity related education in Pakistan: engaging students through the Socratic
463 method of learning. *J Biosaf Biosec*. 2021;3(1):22-27. doi:10.1016/j.jobb.2021.03.003.
- 464 13. Elhadidy M, El-Tholoth M, Brocard AS. Implementation of active learning approach
465 to teach biorisk management and dual-use research of concern in Egypt. *Appl Biosaf*.
466 2019;24(2):100-110. doi:10.1177/1535676019836998. PMID: 36033939; PMCID:
467 PMC9387730.
- 468 14. Qasmi SA, Zafar M, Pirzada S, Saldera KA, Turabi A. Assessment and impact of a
469 biosecurity course in raising the awareness of students at the Jinnah Postgraduate
470 Medical Center, Pakistan. *J Biosaf Biosec*. 2019;1(2):93-97.
471 doi:10.1016/j.jobb.2019.09.004.
- 472 15. World Health Organization. Laboratory leadership competency framework. Geneva:
473 WHO; 2019. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO.
- 474 16. R Core Team (2023). *_R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing_*. R
475 Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <<https://www.R-project.org/>>.